

CLIMATE CHANGE AND ITS ROLE IN THE TWO COUNTRIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6880950>

Annotation: Climate change is a problem that stands out in our time for being more important than any other problem. From changes in weather conditions that threaten food production, rising sea levels, increasing the risk of devastating floods, climate change is deteriorating globally and at an unprecedented level. Without strict measures today, adaptation to these consequences in the future will be more complicated and costly. This article is about climate cooperation between the US and China. Drought, greenhouses, climate change have encouraged the two countries to cooperate.

Keywords: "China is committed to developing a national methane action plan for COP27", US-China climate declaration, greenhouse gas emissions, carbon energy transition, field of environmental protection.

The climate cooperation between the US and China plays an important role, despite the differences between the countries on a number of issues. This was stated 13th Iyul on Wednesday by US Special Envoy for Climate Affairs, former Secretary of State John Kerry, speaking in Glasgow at the 26th Conference of the Parties to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change COP27 after the release of a joint US-China climate statement. "The US and China have no shortage of differences, but on climate issues, cooperation is the only way to achieve our goals. We cannot achieve our goals without both countries working together," Kerry said, adding that the fight against climate change plays an extremely important role. He called the US and China "the world's two largest emitters of greenhouse gases". At a press conference, the ex-secretary of state said that Washington and Beijing agreed to reduce methane emissions and reduce the use of coal in industry this decade "as soon as possible." "China is committed to developing a national methane action plan for COP27," he said, speaking of a conference to be held next year. In addition, the special envoy explained, the parties "agreed on the need to ensure compliance with relevant laws governing deforestation."

The joint US-China climate declaration, he said, is "a step to build on" in terms of reducing greenhouse gas emissions. It also "demonstrates the urgent need to cooperate" in the fight against climate change. China, as the largest developing country, must actively fight its own air pollution, while the largest developed nation, the United States, urgently needs to reduce the damage from droughts

and hurricanes that have become regular. Against the background of forecasts of a fourfold increase in the number of natural disasters due to the greenhouse effect, concern for creating a prosperous environment for posterity has no doubt become a common aspiration of China and the United States.

The fight against climate change is inextricably linked with the construction of a human community with a common destiny. Before the UN climate conference scheduled for later this year in Paris, China and the United States agreed to work together to minimize the damage from "one of the most serious threats to humanity."

At the last meeting on the sidelines of the APEC summit in Beijing in 2014, the leaders, among other things, announced that states would set their own goals to combat climate change for the period after 2020. They also agreed to push for a new climate deal at the upcoming conference in Paris. At the last meeting on the sidelines of the APEC summit in Beijing in 2014, the leaders, among other things, announced that states would set their own goals to combat climate change for the period after 2020. They also agreed to push for a new climate deal at the upcoming conference in Paris. "These announcements open up new opportunities for a low carbon energy transition and for the development of new and renewable energy sources. The two countries are working together not only to prevent our harm to the planet, but, more importantly, to lay the foundations for a sustainable development," said Liu Zhu, a researcher at Harvard University whose professional background is greenhouse gas emissions research, in an interview with Xinhua.

China and the US have announced their own targets for reducing greenhouse gas emissions. In June this year, in accordance with the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change, China introduced the "Individual National Contribution /INDC/" document, setting a goal of reducing carbon dioxide emissions by 60-65 percent by 2020, per unit of GDP compared to 2005. "China is ready to make joint efforts with the parties concerned to reach a comprehensive and balanced agreement based on the principles of common but differentiated responsibilities, fairness and inherent opportunities at the Paris summit," Chinese Foreign Ministry spokesman Hong Lei said at a daily briefing on Tuesday. "Since there is not much time left before the summit, the parties should speed up negotiations," the diplomat added. The US administration, for its part, unveiled the Clean Energy Plan in August, in which President Barack Obama set a goal of cutting greenhouse gas emissions from US power plants by

almost a third over the next 15 years, calling it "the most important step for the United States to combat climate change".

Although China and the United States have made joint and separate efforts, there are still many challenges for future cooperation on climate change issues, the main of which is the question of how the two countries can find a balance between economic development and environmental protection by achieving mutual benefit in bilateral cooperation in the above fields. "In this direction, [China and the United States] do not have a shortcut," Liu Zhu said, noting that both sides should continue to step up efforts in the areas of technical innovation, education, and efficiency improvement. The reduction of carbon dioxide emissions inevitably frustrates the economic development plans of developing countries. This fact not only speaks of the validity of the "common but differentiated responsibility" principle, but also calls on developed countries to provide developing countries with the necessary financial and technical support to reduce carbon dioxide emissions.

At the same time, Liu Zhu believes that strengthening cooperation between China and the United States researchers is important because it will allow the parties to "accurately assess the technical performance and carbon emissions", as well as consistently provide information to developed countries for the transfer of technology and funds to developing countries. According to Cui Tiankai, China and the United States have already realized that strengthening cooperation in the field of environmental protection not only does not have a negative impact on economic growth, but, on the contrary, creates more jobs and opportunities and leads to business cooperation in other areas.

Cui Tiankai cited the example that Chinese enterprises can supply equipment to US companies in the solar and wind energy sectors, and American products and industry-specific knowledge will help meet China's demand for the construction of a large number of nuclear power plants, as well as stimulate the development of clean carbon technology and increase opportunities natural gas production and consumption. Republicans in Congress, who opposed the initiative of B. Obama, insist that this plan will harm the country's coal industry and lead to an increase in electricity prices. At the same time, the head of the US Environmental Protection Agency, Gina McCarthy, spoke out in support of the Clean Energy plan, which, in her opinion, will help to drastically reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

In summary, Xi Jinping's trip to the United States greatly encourages the two countries to make greater joint efforts to combat climate change and promote

cooperation in the fields of energy conservation and carbon reduction, which will lead to more effective reduction of carbon dioxide emissions and other countries of the world. Since 2008, China has ranked first in the world in terms of annual greenhouse gas emissions, almost twice as high as the United States. Beijing emitted 10.2 billion tons of CO₂ (5.3 billion tons in the US) in 2019, accounting for almost 28 percent of global emissions, according to the statistics portal Our World in Data, which features experts from Oxford University. But these data alone are not enough to place particular blame on China for global warming.

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